

A New Photochemical Redox Method for the Estimation of Thallium(III) in the Presence of High Chloride Ion Concentrations catalysed by Iron(III)

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A photochemical titrimetric method is described for the determination of thallium(III) with oxalate in 0.5 M perchloric acid and in the presence of high chloride (6.0 mmol) and 0.001–0.002 mmol of iron(III) as catalyst. Thallium(III) is reduced to thallium(I) photochemically with oxalic acid in perchloric acid medium in the presence of excess of chloride using iron(III) as catalyst. The reduced thallium(I) is determined bromatometrically in 1.5–2.0 M HCl in the presence of methyl orange as indicator. The catalytic activity of iron(III) is attributed to its capacity to photochemically oxidise oxalate and the subsequent reaction between thallium(III) and iron(II) in chloride medium. A detailed mechanism is proposed for the catalytic reaction.

Even though there are some reductimetric methods available for the determination of thallium(III), there is no convenient method available for the estimation of thallium(III) in the presence of high concentration of chloride ions. The reduction of thallium(III) in the presence of halide ion becomes rather difficult due to the decrease in the Tl^{III}/Tl^I potential¹ with increase in chloride concentration. Determination of thallium(III) in the presence of chloride ions sometimes becomes essential. Sagi and Rao² described a method for the estimation of thallium(III) in HCl medium by reduction with tin(II). However, this method requires inert atmosphere to store the reductant and also the reaction itself has to be carried out in oxygen-free atmosphere. With a view to describe a convenient method for the determination of thallium(III) in chloride medium, an investigation is carried out on the photochemical reduction of thallium(III) with oxalate in the presence of iron(III) and chloride ions.

Results and Discussion

Sagi *et al.*³ reported a photochemical redox method for the estimation of thallium(III) with oxalic acid. In their investigations they have noticed

that, with increase in oxalic acid concentration the rate of the reaction increased, while higher perchloric acid concentration has retarded the rate of the reaction. The optimum chloride and bromide concentrations for a quick progress of the reaction were reported to be twice and half to that of the thallium(III) content in the reaction mixture, respectively. However, if the concentration of the halide ion is increased the reaction slowed down and still further increase completely stopped the reaction.

In the present communication, an attempt is made to bring out the photochemical reduction of thallium(III) with oxalic acid in higher chloride concentrations and investigated the effect of the volume of the reaction mixture, concentration of oxalate and catalytic activity of iron(III) in this reaction. The results are presented in Tables 1–3. The optimum conditions for acid concentration is fixed at 0.5 M perchloric acid, as the reaction is found to be faster in lower acid concentration³. Still lower acid concentrations are avoided so as to minimise the possibility of hydrolysis of thallium(III). The total volume of the reaction mixture is kept at 100 ml as the reaction is faster in higher dilutions (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TOTAL VOLUME OF THE REACTION MIXTURE ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF THALLIUM(III) WITH OXALIC ACID IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Amount of Tl^{III} = 0.1 mmol, Amount of oxalic acid = 0.8 mmol, Amount of chloride = 4.0 mmol, Concentration of $HClO_4$ = 0.5 M

Total volume of reaction mixture	Time required for complete reduction of Tl^{III}
ml	min
50	35
75	20
100	15

The data in Table 2 reveal that with the increasing concentration of chloride ion, the time required for the completion of the reaction is also increased, but this retardation effect is nullified by the increase in oxalate concentration.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CHLORIDE AND OXALATE ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF THALLIUM(III) IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Amount of Tl^{III} mmol	Amount of oxalate mmol	Amount of chloride mmol	$[HClO_4]$ M	Time required for complete reduction min
0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	8
0.1	0.2	1.0	0.5	10
0.1	0.2	4.0	0.5	40
0.1	0.2	6.0	0.5	70
0.1	0.4	4.0	0.5	20
0.1	0.4	6.0	0.5	45
0.1	0.8	4.0	0.5	15
0.1	0.8	6.0	0.5	30
0.1	1.6	4.0	0.5	10
0.1	1.6	6.0	0.5	15
0.1	1.6	8.0	0.5	25
0.1	1.6	10.0	0.5	35

It can be further seen (Table 3) that the presence of small quantities iron(III) as catalyst also contributes to the quick progress of the reaction. The iron(III) content (0.001–0.002 mmol) is found to be quite suitable as it does not consume any noticeable titrant even after complete reduction to iron(II).

It may be noted that there is no considerable reaction in dark even under the optimum experimental conditions at room temperature. Further, the reaction is not complete when exposed to light for an initial period of 1 min and subsequently kept in dark. The reaction rate becomes almost negligible the moment the light is cut off. The reaction mixture kept under light from mercury vapour lamp initiated polymerization in acrylonitrile indicating the formation of free radicals. Such free radical formation is not noticed in dark. Under the present experimental conditions, iron(II) is found to be as effective a catalyst as iron(III). In the presence of iron(II) also no significant reaction is noticed in dark. Based on these observations a probable mechanism is proposed for this photochemical reaction :

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IRON(III) ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF THALLIUM(III) WITH OXALIC ACID IN HIGH CHLORIDE CONCENTRATION IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Amount of Tl^{III} mmol	Amount of oxalate mmol	Amount of chloride mmol	Amount of Fe^{III} mmol	$[HClO_4]$ M	Time required for complete reduction min
0.1	0.8	4.0	0.001	0.5	5
0.1	0.8	6.0	0.001	0.5	15
0.1	1.6	4.0	0.001	0.5	5
0.1	1.6	6.0	0.001	0.5	10
0.1	1.6	8.0	0.001	0.5	15
0.1	1.6	10.0	0.001	0.5	25
0.1	1.6	6.0	0.002	0.5	7
0.1	1.6	8.0	0.002	0.5	10
0.1	1.6	10.0	0.002	0.5	15
0.1	0.8	6.0	0.002	0.5	5
0.1	0.8	6.0	0.004	0.5	5
0.1	1.6	10.0	0.004	0.5	15

Rao *et al.*⁴ reported the photochemical reduction of iron(III) with oxalic acid and attributed the reaction to the photochemical redox decomposition of iron(III)-oxalato complex. The reaction can be represented by equation (1), the products being iron(II) and oxalate free radicals. The free radicals thus formed can react with Tl^{3+} or Tl^{2+} as per equation (2) or (5). Tl^{2+} formed in some of these reactions can also react with oxalate ion to produce Tl^+ and $C_2O_4^{\cdot-}$ as per equation (3). The possibility of the reaction between free Fe^{3+} and $C_2O_4^{\cdot-}$ can be excluded as Fe^{3+} exists as the oxalato complex under the present experimental conditions. The present reaction is catalysed by Fe^{3+} even when present in traces. This catalytic effect may be due to the production of unstable reactive species, Tl^{2+} and $C_2O_4^{\cdot-}$, continuously. These unstable free radicals in turn may react with Tl^{3+} producing Tl^{2+} and CO_2 (equation 2). Tl^{2+} itself being unstable and being a powerful oxidant can even oxidise Mn^{2+} to Mn^{3+} , can react with $C_2O_4^{\cdot-}$, thus producing Tl^+ and $C_2O_4^{\cdot-}$ (equation 3) or with Fe^{2+} producing Fe^{3+} (equation 4). The free radicals can also react with Tl^{2+} as per equation (5), thus terminating the reaction.

The reason for the absence of the reaction in dark may be attributed to the absence of the active species responsible for the reaction. Further, it may be noticed that when the reaction mixture is exposed to light for an initial period and then kept in dark, the reaction is not complete. This may once again be due to the termination of further production of the reactive species. This shows that mere initiation of the reaction is not enough to bring out the completion of the photochemical reduction.

It is also found that Fe^{2+} is as effective a catalyst as Fe^{3+} . This is probably due to the reaction between Tl^{3+} and Fe^{2+} (equation 6) which gives rise to Fe^{3+} and active Tl^{2+} species. As predicted by different workers^{5,6}, the noncomplementary reaction between thallium(III) and iron(II) is slow. However, in the presence of high concentrations of chloride ion the above reaction is accelerated⁵ thus facilitating the for-

mation of reactive Tl^{2+} and Fe^{3+} required for the photochemical production of oxalate free radicals.

Experimental

Thallium(I) solution was oxidised⁷ with excess of bromine water in the presence of HCl. The excess bromine was then boiled off, cooled to room temperature and thallium precipitated as thallium(III) hydroxide using NH_4OH . Then it was filtered through G_4 sintered glass funnel and washed free from halides (Cl^- and Br^-). The thallium(III) hydroxide precipitate was washed free from halides, dissolved in appropriate quantity of corresponding acid of known concentration, and standardised^{8,9}.

The precision of the proposed method is ascertained from the values obtained by actual determination of 6 replicates of a fixed amount of the compound. The average value of these determinations, the true and the relative standard deviation are reported.

A 0.01 M Fe^{III} solution was prepared by dissolving ferric ammonium sulphate (A.R.) in water containing dilute H_2SO_4 ; it was diluted further to give a working solution of 0.001M. Free radicals were tested¹⁰ using acrylonitrile. G.R. (E. Merck) perchloric acid was used.

Photochemical studies : The photochemical reactions were carried out under the light using Philips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (125 W). The solutions were irradiated in colourless glass beakers (Corning) at a distance of 0.15 m from the lamp.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.20 mmol of Tl^{III} , chloride (6.0 mmol), Fe^{III} (1.0 – 2.0×10^{-3} mmol), oxalate (1.6 mmol), enough perchloric acid to maintain 0.5M were added and diluted to 100 ml. The solution was stirred and exposed to light for 10 min and then concentrated HCl (15 ml) and methyl orange indicator (0.1 mg/ml) were added and titrated with 0.05N potassium bromate (1.392 g dm^{-3}). The titre corresponded to Tl^I formed in the reaction mixture, corresponding to Tl^{III} present in the sample. The

results (Table 4) show that the method is quite satisfactory and can be applied for estimation of thallium(III) in the presence of high concentration of chloride ions under mild experimental conditions.

TABLE 4—ESTIMATION OF Tl^{III}

[HClO₄] = 0.5 M Fe^{III} = 1.0–2.0 × 10⁻³ mmol, Oxalic acid = 1.6 mmol, Cl⁻ = 6.0 mmol

Tl ^{III} taken mmol	Tl ^{III} found mmol	% of error
0.050	0.049	2.0
0.060	0.060	Nil
0.070	0.069	1.4
0.080	0.081	1.2
0.090	0.089	1.1
0.100	0.099	1.0
0.120	0.120	Nil
0.150	0.148	1.3
0.180	0.180	Nil
0.200	0.198	1.0
Average value = 0.0988 mmol (0.1000 mmol)		R.S.D. = 0.1427%

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